

ISSN 2230- 9373

Volume-VI, Issue-1

January-March, 2023

A KEY TO SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT-SOLAR POWERED WATER COOLING SYSTEM

Durgamadhab Swain, Debayani Mishra

Department of Electrical Engineering, ABIT, Cuttack, Odisha

E-mail:- durgamadhab.ee@gmail.com, debayanim@gmail.com

Abstract-

The idea of solar-powered water coolers is explained in this article. The system consists of solar panels, two low-energy fans, a clay water tank, a thermally sealed box, and pipes. The water temperatures at both ends were evaluated following the union of these components. The earliest data indicated a temperature reduction of almost 17 degrees Celsius. This is accomplished by utilizing the sun's free energy. In addition, the use of solar cooling as a potential option for driving an evaporative cooler to chill the drinking water supply has been forced by worries over the negative environmental impact of utilizing fossil fuels.

Key Words: *Renewable Energy, Sustainable Development, Solar Water Cooler*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, a nation's prosperity is determined by its energy consumption; the gross domestic product (GDP) of a country is directly proportional to its energy consumption. Consequently, the demand for energy resources increases daily. Renewable energy sources (sun, air, and wind) and non-renewable energy sources (fossil fuels) are the two primary categories of energy resources (coal, petroleum). Non-renewable energy resources accelerate industrial expansion, but their supply is limited by nature. Loss and degradation of fossil fuels has required an immediate search for alternative energy sources in order to meet the energy demands of the near future and future generations. Renewable energy is

energy produced from renewable natural resources, such as sunshine, wind, rain, tides, and geothermal heat (naturally replenished). In 2006, around 19% of the world's final energy consumption was derived from renewable sources, with 12% coming from traditional biomass sources such as wood-burning. The second greatest renewable source was hydroelectricity, contributing 4%, followed by solar hot water/heating, which contributed 1.6%. Modern technologies, including geothermal energy, wind energy, solar energy, and ocean energy, accounted for around 0.7% of total energy consumption. Concerns about climate change, combined with high oil costs, peak oil, and growing government support, are driving an increase in renewable energy legislation, incentives, and commercialization. As part of its effort to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, which are partly to blame for global warming, European Union leaders struck an agreement in principle in March 2007 that 22 percent of their nations' energy should come from renewable sources by 2020.

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growing government support, are driving an increase in renewable energy legislation, incentives, and commercialization. As part of their efforts to reduce carbon dioxide emissions, which are partly to blame for global warming, European Union leaders struck an agreement in principle in March 2007 that 22 percent of their nations' energy should come from renewable fuels by 2020.

Solar energy is the most promising long-term solution for fulfilling the ever-increasing need for energy among the numerous available choices. This resource's key drawbacks include its low intensity, sporadic nature, and lack of availability at night. Even. Despite these constraints, Solar energy seems to be the most promising source of renewable energy. Solar energy is an inexhaustible supply. The sun generates large quantities of renewable solar energy that can be turned to heat and power. Solar energy is believed to have numerous applications, including water heating, air heating, building air conditioning, solar refrigeration, photovoltaic units, green houses, power generation from photo-chemical, power production, solar furnaces, and photo-biological variations, to name a few. Among these, energy from sun the usage of solar energy for power generation and heating is currently the focus of active research.

Employing solar photovoltaic cells to directly convert solar energy to electricity is the most effective method for harvesting solar energy. In this System of energy Conversion that involves direct conversion of solar radiation into electricity, sunlight strikes solar cells. In the step of transmutation into thermodynamic form, nothing exists. The photovoltaic effect is the formation of an electromotive force as a result of ionizing radiation absorption [3]-[5]. Solar cells are energy conversion devices that utilize the photovoltaic effect to transform sunlight into electricity [6],[7].

In recent times, solar cell has generated power that has garnered significant attention as one of the most promising alternative energy sources. PV's transforms solar energy to electricity and its non-polluting nature are the primary reasons for this growing interest. The broad use of photovoltaic energy has been hindered by economic concerns. The cheap cost of conventional electricity has precluded the development of an all-encompassing PV technology. PV generating can now only be justified in exceptional circumstances, primarily in distant places.

2.SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS

In this research paper, the cooler is a component that both heats and cools water and dispenses it. There are various varieties of water coolers on the market, including wall-mounted water dispensers, bottom-load water dispensers, tabletop water dispensers, and freestanding water dispensers.

Fig.1 Schematic Diagram of Water Disposer

These gravity-powered systems have a controlled water dispensing mechanism. A solar water dispenser is a device that uses solar energy to heat, cool, and dispense water. These gravity-powered systems have a controlled water dispensing mechanism. Any device, pipe, container, or faucet that draws water from a storage tank and delivers it using solar energy is a solar water dispenser. The word water dispenser encompasses a wide range of goods, including a simple water jug with a tap, a sink faucet, and an on-board water dispenser feature on a refrigerator [4]. However, solar water dispensers are often devices that can accept a large prefilled water bottle and feature a faucet for pouring both hot and cold water. When the design of the water dispenser includes a compressor to cool the water, it is also a water cooler. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the evaporation concept is used to chill the drinking water in this investigation.

The water cooler unit consists of the following components

2.1 Solar Panel

A solar panel is a group of solar photovoltaic modules mounted on a framework and electrically connected. Typically, each module's DC output power under standard test conditions (STC) is rated between 100 and 320 watts. Given the same rated output, an 8%-efficient 230-watt module will have twice as much surface area as a 16%-efficient 230-watt module. Since a single solar module can only provide a limited quantity of energy, the majority of systems consist of numerous modules. Typically, a photovoltaic system consists of a solar panel or array of solar modules, an inverter, and occasionally a battery and/or solar tracker and connector cable.

2.2 Battery

A battery consists of a zinc casing (the negative electrode), a carbon rod in the centre of the cell (the positive electrode), and an electrolyte paste in the space between them. Today's most prevalent battery type is the dry cell battery. There are a variety of battery kinds, ranging from very big height batteries to miniature versions used in wristwatches and calculators. Although they differ greatly in composition and structure, they all operate according to the same principle.

2.3 Charge Regulator

The charge regulator or battery regulator regulates the rate at which current is added to or released from electric batteries. It prevents overcharging and may prevent overvoltage, both of which can reduce battery performance or longevity and provide a potential safety risk. In order to maintain battery life, it may also prevent a battery from being completely drained (deep draining) or perform controlled discharges, depending on battery technology. A solar panel is a group of solar photovoltaic modules mounted on a framework and electrically connected.

2.4 Water Cooler

The water cooler operates on the basis of the vapor's compression refrigeration cycle. The compressor compresses the refrigerant before delivering it to the condenser, which is cooled by a fan. After being cooled by a condenser, the high-pressure liquid is collected in a receiver before proceeding to the expansion valve. The expansion valve absorbs the needed amount of refrigerant based on the evaporator's load.

3. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The research paper proposes a cooler act as a component that cools, and distributes drinking water. The water dispensers, bottom-load water dispensers, tabletop water dispensers, freestanding water dispensers, and direct-piping water dispensers are available on the market. These gravity-controlled units have a controlled water dispensing mechanism. A solar water dispenser is a device that uses solar energy to heat, cool, and dispense water. These units are controlled by gravity systems have a controlled water dispensing mechanism. The proposed project uses a device, pipe, container, or faucet that pulls water from a storage tank and dispenses it using solar energy. The dispenser encompasses a wide range of goods, including a tap that has a jug, a sink, and an on-board water dispenser feature on a refrigerator [4]. However, solar water dispensers typically refer to a device that can accommodate a large prefilled water bottle and includes a faucet for dispensing both hot and cold water. When the water dispenser's design incorporates a compressor to cool the water, it is also a water cooler.

As the refrigerant passes through the expansion valve, its temperature drops significantly (by as much as -10°C). Its pressure also decreases. The liquid refrigerant then flows through the evaporator coils that surround the water tank (water may be stored in it). The liquid refrigerant in the coils absorbs the water's latent heat, leaving the water chilled.

As the liquid refrigerant runs through the evaporator coils, it is transformed into vapor, and by the time it exits the coils, it is almost all transformed into dry vapor. This vapour is subsequently compressed by the compressor. Thus, this cycle is perpetually repeated. The cooled water can be emptied and replaced with new water for cooling. The working of water cooler is explained in Fig.2

Fig.2 Working Principle of Water Cooler

Two single-phase induction motors are utilized in water coolers. The first is a fan motor, whereas the second is a compressor motor. The motor of the fan is a capacitor-start motor, however its capacitor (CF) remains in the circuit throughout operation as well. The purpose of the fan motor is to cool the condenser using forced air circulation. Fan-driven compressor circulation. The motor of the compressor is a capacitor-start and capacitor-run motor. The compressor motor's capacitor (CC) has a greater capacity than the fan motor's. The capacitor enhances the motor's power factor and starting torque. The overload protection and thermostat are also used in water cooler. When the water attains desired temperature, the thermostat dipped in water chamber operates and disconnects the power supply to the motor described in Fig.3

Fig.3 Water Cooler Electrical Circuit

In an evaporative water cooler, cooling is achieved through the evaporation of flowing outside water, but there is a heat exchanger between the wet air and the dry air supply. As shown in Fig. 4, the heat exchanger can be a wall coated with a water-resistant layer to prevent the introduction of moisture into the supply air. The evaporation of the surface's moisture by the hot air that acts as a coolant to the surface. The cold surface interchanges the hot air with supply, resulting in a cold-water supply

Fig.4 Evaporative Water Cooler

One more benefit of this solar-powered evaporative cooler is that it does not place additional strain on the electricity grid during high demand periods. As vapor compression-based water coolers can account for a significant portion of the electricity required to power compressors. In residential locations, it is projected that vapour compression-based refrigerators account for more than 30 percent of the overall electric energy demand during summer peak hours. Especially on hot days and in nations where grid-connected compression cooling systems provide a great deal of cooling and low temperature storage. Thus, coolers and refrigerators utilizing the vapour compression technology might have a significant impact on the electrical networks. In the summer, a period of extremely high temperatures resulted to an 8% rise in electricity consumption due to an overload on the electricity supply system, and daily average energy demand might establish new records. A water cooler is installed at an educational institute implementing this technology represented in the following Fig.5 as follows

Fig.5 Water Cooler

4. CONCLUSION

Reducing the grid's load as well as global warming and its repercussions are of great concern nowadays. If a system for cooling drinking water could be built to overcome these issues, it will be a significant accomplishment. In the present study, a novel design of a solar-powered water cooler is presented that makes advantage of freely accessible solar energy, thereby relieving the strain on the electrical grid. The system uses a solar trough collector, an evaporation cycle as opposed to a vapor's compression cycle, and environmentally friendly absorbent refrigerant couples to eliminate the need for a compressor. Electricity consumption is lowered to a certain amount.

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